

THE DEVOLPOMENT OF PARA VOLLEYBALL AND ITS COMING IN TO UZBEKISTAN

Joldasbaeva Aziza

Trainee teacher Nukus Branch of the Uzbek state university of physical
culture and Sports Uzbekistan, Karakalpakstan, Nukus
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Annotation: The article gives information about the short story of the Para Volleyball and its coming in to Uzbekistan. Furthermore, there will be outlined views about disabled people's interests in physical activities and sports.

Keywords: Mass sports, family sport, activities, para volleyball

As our government become independent, more attention has been given to develop and populatize different types of the national sport with international sport games. Noaadays, the attentions for sport and physical activities rise year by year. In our country, there are some decisions and orders issued in the field of sprots and physical activities might be an example to it.

According to the decision No201 adopted on april 11, 2022, by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, given about the promotion of mass sport compititions among young people in our country, and the following should be defined as the main directions of mass sports development:

- strengthening the material and technical base for youth mass sports in neighborhoods and providing sport facilities with modern sport equipment, as well as creating appropriate sport infrostructure for young people with disabilities;
- forming a healthy lifestyle among broad sections of the population, especially among young ones, increasing the participation of young people in mass sports by organizing mass sports competitions among them;
- creating conditions in neighborhoods and recreating parks for families regularly engaged in public sports and introducing mechanisms to encourage family sports;
- to adequately encourage the work of physical education teachers of general secindary schools and trainers of sport's educational institutions, whose students are winners and prize-winners during public sport events, and to create conditions for their activities.

Moreover, nowadays in the Relublic of Uzbekistan is taking steps to develop volleyball. Especially, to develop this type of sport like volleyball in the country and make its population interest in it, the production of several legal and regulatory documents is a clear proof of this.

Law No 513-XII of the Relublic of Uzbekistan "On physical Education and Sports" adopted on January 14, 1992 and supplements to the law adopted on September 4, 2015 made into a basic guideline.

The main goal of this is make person achieve healthy lifestyle and become heathy. The physical activities and sports plays an important role in making future generations healthy. Ministry of health of the whole world works on the basis of this slogan. In this regard, today in the countries of the world, along with playing sports, new types of sport games are invented or some types that are disappeared are being reimplemented.

It is no exaggeration to say that the number of sports are developing in our country as well. The reason for this is the importance of physical education and training in the organization of a healthy lifestyle and the maintenance of public health, as well as the efforts of Resident Sh. Mirziyoyev in this regard true policy.

According to the information below there will be given some types of sports as example.

Para-volleyball is considered as a specially designed sport for people with disabilities and was invented for the first time in the name of the country.

Later it gradually developed. Of course, through this type of sport, we will be able to organize interesting sport games among the disabled youth and thereby arouse their interest in sports. Today in all regions of our republic, even in remote rural areas, all opportunities and conditions have been created for doing physical exercises or sports.

It is worth noting that volleyball is of incomparable importance in acceleration of mass health care throughout our country. In fact, volleyball is recognized as the most popular sport in the world. In the educational institutions of our republic, volleyball is included in the curriculum as a science and a means of health. And also this type of sport is included in mass sport competitions like "Umid nihollari", "Barkamol avlod" and "Universiada". [1]

But the further expansion of mass volleyball and the improvement of the efficiency of training highly qualified volleyball players is determined by the quality of personnel training in this specialty. The purposeful solution of these problems depends on the potential of the used educational literature and lessons based on comprehensive, new scientific and methodical information.

The rules of the game: sitting volleyball is Paralympic sport that uses a smaller court and a lower net. It provides an ideal activity for groups of mixed abilities. How to play this paravolleyball.

The most interesting thing is that everyone even disabled can play it. Currently, as a sport's coach, I am developing this sport in Uzbekistan, especially in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

In the regard, there is organized a team included disabled youth from Karakalpakstan. In September 2022, a conversation with young disabled people was held in Muynoq district, the most remote region of Karakalpakstan, and it was agreed to engage in this type of sport with them based on their ability and desire. The most interesting thing is that everyone even disabled can play it. Currently, as a sport's coach, I am developing this sport in Uzbekistan, especially in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

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Sitting volleyball originated in the Netherlands in 1956. After entering as a "demonstration" sport during the 1976 Paralympic Games in Toronto, Canada, Sitting Volleyball was first included in competition at the 1980 Paralympic Games in Arnhem, Netherlands. It has been in every Paralympic Games since. In 1984, the United States participated in its first Paralympic Games in New York City. In the 2004 Paralympics, held in Athens, Greece, the U.S. Men's Team finished 6th, and the U.S. Women's Team finished 3rd, taking home a bronze medal. Both finishes were the best ever for the U.S.

Sitting volleyball is currently played in more than 60 countries world-wide in a two-stage league system, where non-disabled athletes can also participate. On April 2nd, 2005, the first

ever Club Sitting Volleyball tournament was held in Omaha, Nebraska. At this tournament, three teams participated: one fully disabled team (from Omaha, Nebraska), one able-bodied team (from Omaha, Nebraska), and one combined disabled and able-bodied team (from Oklahoma City, Oklahoma). This was the official starting point for Club Sitting Volleyball in the United States. Since 2005, there have been many other club teams—both able-bodied and disabled—started across the United States. Each year the tournament has doubled in size of teams and players and still looking for more across the region or nation [5].

Figure 1. The first para volleyball players.

The rules of the game: sitting volleyball is Paralympic sport that uses a smaller court and a lower net. It provides an ideal activity for groups of mixed abilities. How to play this paravolleyball

1. Played by 2 teams of 6 players (or any suitable number). Most of the rules are the same as the standing game, but the main exceptions are:
2. Players must keep part of their bottom in contact with the floor when playing the ball; and players are allowed to block the serve:
3. Play the ball using fingers, hands or arms: 4. Teams try to send the ball over the net so that it touches the ground on their opponent's side:
5. Rallies continue until the ball touches the ground, the ball goes 'out', or their opponents fail to return it:
6. A point is scored if the ball lands in the opponents' court or they cannot return the ball:
7. Normally, there is a maximum of three hits per team then the ball must cross the net:
8. Ideas that can keep the rallies going for longer; for example, some players outside the court area who hit stray balls back into play:
9. Ways of ensuring that all the players are equally involved:

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most remote region of Karakalpakstan, and it was agreed to engage in this type of sport with them based on their ability and desire.

Figure 2. The first day of exercising with disabled young in Muynoq region.

On top of this, today in the capital of Karakalpakstan in Nukus I have organized courses for disabled youth in order to develop this type of sport there. This club is directly aimed at practicing para volleyball, where we work in two teams. They are very ambitious and like to be always on the move. I also love my job, so working with them gives me great pleasure.

In conclusion, mamlakatimizda ushbu sport turini yanada rivojlantirishga ozmuncha bo'lsa ham o'z hissamni qo'shish niyatida ekanligimni, shuningdek imkoniyati cheklangan yoshlar o'rtasida para voleybolchilar jamoalarni tashkil qilib ular bilan bugungi kunda muntazam shug'illanib kelayotganimiz haqidagi fikrlarni bo'lishish, qolaversa maqolani o'qib qiziqayotganlarga ushbu sportni rivojiga hissa qo'shishini so'rab mazkur maqolaga yakun yasayman.

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